

Ahtola Industrial Research Project - Advanced Hybrid Method for the Tolerance Analysis of Complex Systems

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Abstract

Tolerancing decisions can profoundly impact the quality, the cost of the product and the number of scraps in mass production. Designers want tight tolerances to assure product performance; manufacturers prefer loose tolerances to reduce cost. There is a critical need for a quantitative design tool for specifying tolerances. Tolerance analysis brings the engineering design requirements and manufacturing capabilities together in a common model, where the effects of tolerance specifications on both design and manufacturing requirements can be evaluated quantitatively.

Current commercial software are not able to provide a tolerance analysis of complex overconstrained mechanism without simplifying the behavior model. The aim of the AHTOLA project is to provide methods to treat industrial cases using complex numerical modeling of mechanical behavior. This project is centered on problem of complementary industrial partners (Pierburg, Valeo SE, Radiall SA) from various fields of application (automotive for Valeo SE and Pierburg, aeronautic for Radiall SA).

The main scientific challenge concerns the development of hybrid approaches mixing worst case and probabilistic approaches to propagate stochastic and epistemic uncertainties for tolerance analysis (stochastic uncertainties = component variations ; epistemic uncertainties = gap configurations). The challenge is the deal between both and the probability computation in an acceptable computer time and managing the accuracy of the results.

1. Introduction

As technology increases and performance requirements continually tighten, the cost and the required precision of assemblies increase as well. There is a strong need for increased attention to tolerance design in order to enable high-precision assemblies to be manufactured at lower costs. Due to the variations associated with manufacturing process, it is not possible to attain the theoretical dimensions in a repetitive manner. It causes a degradation of functional characteristics of the product. In order to ensure the desired behavior and the functional requirements of the system in spite of variations, the component features are assigned a tolerance zone within which the value of the feature i.e. situation and intrinsic lie.

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Therefore, tolerance analysis is a key element in industry for improving product quality and decreasing the manufacturing cost. In addition, it participates to an eco-aware attitude since it allows industrials to manage and reduce scrap in production. Tolerance analysis concerns the verification of the value of functional requirements after tolerance has been specified on each component. Currently, this verification is totally dependent on the models chosen before. Currently, trial runs or very simple simulation models (1D linear tolerance charts for example) are used to check the quality criterion. This approach can be called into question: the trial runs are very costly and time consuming. Researchers have recognized the inefficiency of such simple simulation models based on explicit system response function which represents the variation accumulation. For complex systems, determination of explicit system response function is very complex, whereas this determination is easy for an open kinematic chain without gap. Research efforts have been devoted to developing an efficient simulation model for tolerance analysis.

Currently, the developed approaches depend on the type of geometrical model and on the type of system response function or simulation model (behavior model). Therefore, their scopes are limited and some problems are not addressed. Moreover, the industrial practices are based on the decomposition of the system kinematic configurations and the simplification of the system response function which are not efficient.

The main objective of the AHTOLA proposal is to develop hybrid approaches for a large scope which are independent of the type of system response function or simulation model (explicit or implicit functions, linear or nonlinear, analytic functions or numerical simulations). Those approaches have to be based on:

- worst case analysis approaches like Solution Space Exploration based on Interval Reduction Methods (Numerical Quantified Constraint Satisfaction Problem – Box consistency, ...), Solution Space Exploration based on Evolutionary Methods (Genetic algorithm, ...), and ... to assess the worst gap configurations regarding to the assemblability and the functional requirements.
- probabilistic approaches like Simulation based method (Monte Carlo Simulation ...), Most probable point based methods (FORM-SORM), Multi-FORM, FORM system, Meta-modeling based method (Kriging ...), to estimate the probability of system conformity based on the process capabilities or statistical distributions of component deviations.

AHTOLA (ANR-11-MONU-013) is a national research project funded by ANR (French National Research Agency). AHTOLA includes 2 academic institutions (Arts et Métiers ParisTech – LCFC and IFMA – Institut Pascal), one Industrial Engineering Consulting firm (PHIMECA) and, finally, three French corporations (Valeo SE, Radiall SA & Pierburg) that represent the constellation of companies operating in highly dynamic industrial sectors.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the mathematical issue and the project position. Section 3 shows a result comparison between two resolution methods.

2. Classification of issues & unified mathematical formulation

In this section, we propose a classification of issues of tolerance analysis based on the type of the behavior model with deviations. The behavior model is the assembly response function which represents the deviation accumulation. It could be an explicit analytic expression, an implicit analytic expression, or numerical simulation for which it is possible to compute a value for some functional characteristics given values of part deviations and gaps.

Tolerance analysis concerns the verification of the value of functional requirements after tolerance has been specified on each component. To do so, it is necessary to simulate the influences of component deviations on the geometrical behavior and the functional characteristics of the mechanism. The geometrical behavior model needs to be aware of the surface deviations of each component (situation deviations and intrinsic deviations) and relative displacements between components according to the gap. The model used in this paper is a parameterization of deviations from theoretic geometry, the real geometry of parts is apprehended by a variation of the nominal geometry.

The deviation of component surfaces, the gaps between components and the functional characteristics are described by parameters:

- $\mathbf{X}=\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$ are the parameters which represent each deviation (such as situation deviations or/and intrinsic deviations) of the components making up the mechanism. Situation deviations correspond with the orientation and position deviation of a substitute surface with respect to a system reference. Intrinsic deviations are specific to the substitute surface, for example the diameter of a pin corresponds with an intrinsic deviation.
- $\mathbf{G}=\{g_1, g_2, \dots, g_m\}$ are the parameters which represent each gap between components. They model the possible displacement in orientation and position between two substitute surfaces.

In the case of analytic formulation, the mathematical formulation of tolerance analysis takes into account the influence of geometrical deviations on the geometrical behavior of the mechanism and on the geometrical product requirements; all these physical phenomena are modeled by constraints on the parameters:

- $C_c(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{G}) = 0$: Composition relations of displacements in the various topological loops express the geometrical behavior of the mechanism. They define compatibility equations between the deviations and the gaps. The set of compatibility equations, obtained by the application of composition relation to the various cycles, makes a system of linear equations. So that the system of linear equations admits a solution, it is necessary that compatibility equations are checked.
- $C_i(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{G}) \leq 0$ and $C_f(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{G}) = 0$: Interface constraints limit the geometrical behavior of the mechanism and characterize non-interference or association between substitute surfaces, which are nominally in contact. These interface constraints limit the gaps between substitute surfaces. In the case of floating contact, the relative positions of substitute surfaces are constrained technologically by the non-interference, the interface constraints result in inequations. In the case of slipping and fixed contact, the relative positions of substitute surfaces are constrained technologically in a given configuration by a mechanical action. An association models this type of contact; the interface constraints result in equations.
- $C_f(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{G}) \leq 0$: The functional requirement limits the orientation and the location between surfaces, which are in functional relation. This requirement is a condition on the relative displacements between these surfaces. This condition could be expressed by constraints, which are inequations.

Mechanism can be divided into two main categories in terms of degree of freedom: isoconstrained mechanisms, and overconstrained mechanisms. Given their impact on the mathematical formulation for the problem of tolerance analysis, a brief discussion of these two types is given by (Ballu, et al., 2009) :

- “Isoconstrained mechanisms are quite easy to grasp. Geometrical deviations within such products do not lead to assembly problems; the deviations are independent and the degrees of freedom catch the deviations. When considering small deviations, functional deviations may be expressed by linear functions of the deviations.”
- “Considering overconstrained mechanisms is much more complex. Assembly problems occur and the expression of the functional deviations is no more linear. Depending on the value of the manufacturing deviations:
 - the assembly is feasible or not;
 - the worst configuration of contacts is not unique for a given functional deviation.
 - For each overconstrained loop, events on the deviations have to be determined:
 - events ensuring assembly,
 - events corresponding to the different worst configurations of contacts. As there are different configurations, the expression of the functional deviation cannot be linear.”

Therefore, in the case of analytic formulation for isoconstrained mechanisms or for simple overconstrained mechanism, it is possible to transform the previous formulation into an explicit function which is the assembly response function: $Y=f(\mathbf{X})$ where Y is the response (characteristic such as gap or functional characteristics) of the assembly. Figure 1. shows an isoconstrained mechanism whose functional characteristic Y is simply expressed by two geometrical deviations:

$$Y = f(\mathbf{X}) = x_2 - x_1 \quad (1)$$

Figure 1. Example of isoconstrained mechanism

However, for overconstrained mechanisms, the functional characteristic cannot be expressed by a simple function. Figure 2. shows an overconstrained mechanism whose characteristic Y depends on the geometrical deviation values and on the configuration of mechanism. That is why the behavior model is considered implicit.

Figure 2. Example of overconstrained mechanism

In such mechanism, a possible compatibility equation is as follows:

$$C_c(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{G}) = x_2 - x_6 - g_1 - g_2 = 0 \quad (2)$$

ration of gaps: “there exists an admissible gap configuration of the mechanism such that the assembly requirement (interface constraints) and the compatibility equations are respected” (Assemblability condition). The probability expression is written as follows:

$$P_A = P(AC) = P(C_c(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{G}) = 0 \cap C_i(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{G}) \leq 0 \cap C_r(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{G}) = 0) \quad (4)$$

$\mathbf{G}$ is considered as free parameters

- P_{FR} : the probability of respect of the functional requirements. Let FC be the event that the functional condition are fulfilled. Once a mechanism assembles, in order to evaluate its performance under the influence of the deviations, it is necessary to describe an additional condition that evaluates its core functioning with respect to the basic product requirements. In terms of the tolerance analysis, the basic requirement becomes the maximum or minimum clearance on a required feature that would have an impact on the mechanism’s performance. The most essential condition therefore becomes that for all the possible gap configurations of the given set of components that assemble together, the functional condition imposed must be respected. In terms of quantification needs, in order to represent all possible gap configurations, the universal quantifier is required: “for all admissible gap configurations of the mechanism, the geometrical behavior and the functional requirement are respected” (functional condition). The probability expression is written as follows:’

$$P_{FR} = P(FC) = P(C_f(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{G}) \leq 0, \forall \mathbf{G} \in \mathbb{R}^m \{C_c(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{G}) = 0 \cap C_i(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{G}) \leq 0 \cap C_r(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{G}) = 0\}) \quad (3)$$

Two analysis methods are used in AHTOLA project:

- Monte Carlo simulation combined with an optimization algorithm in order to find the worst configuration for the functional requirement or to check if there exists a configuration of gaps verifying all constraints.
- The First Order Reliability Method (FORM) for systems is also used. The mechanism is decomposed into its main configurations of contact points. It is then possible to apply a system reliability method. This technique only works when verifying the functional requirement.

3. Industrial application

The application is based on a gear pump, see Figure 4, which has two parts positioned with two pins. The positioning of these two parts has an influence on the angle of both gear axes. The functionality of the pump can be reduced if the assembly precision of the parts is insufficient. Based on this pump, a simplified overconstrained mechanism is studied. Figure 2 shows the mechanism with amplified gaps between parts. The functional condition concerns the deviation of the point G of part (1) with respect to part (2). This point G can be seen as a functional point that is representative of one axis of the gear pump.

Figure 4. Full pump view with the simplified studied mechanism.

Both pins are fixed in part (2), so there are only gaps between part (1) and the pins. The planar contact is assumed to be perfect, so only the kinematic displacements of the joint are considered. Geometrical deviations are applied to surfaces a, b, c and g. Characteristics of the mathematical behavior model are listed below:

- 38 random variables following a Gaussian distribution $X \sim N(\mu X, \sigma X)$.
- 15 gap variables $\mathbf{G}$ which are the optimizations parameters.
- 12 compatibility equations $C_c(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{G}) = 0$
- 4 quadratic interface constraints $C_i(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{G}) \leq 0$ which give $N_c = 160$ interface constraints after applying a linearization procedure.

Table 1. Comparison of results between two resolution methods.

	Monte Carlo simulation		FORM for systems
	Assembly	Functional	Functional
Probability of failure (ppm)	42	9.4	9.3
95% confidence interval	6.9	1.7	-
Computing time	3.5 days	3.5 days	2.35 min

The system method developed in the project is very efficient but it only allows dealing with the functional requirement so far.

4. Conclusion

The AHTOLA project aims at providing methodological solutions to deal with the tolerance analysis of overconstrained mechanisms. Currently, commercial software are not able to consider this kind of mechanism without great simplifications. The goal of the project is to propose a global method able to model the geometrical behavior of overconstrained mechanism using constraints on parameters and to provide the probability of failure using efficient methods. The solution method includes a Monte Carlo simulation combined with an optimization algorithm, this technique is able to deal with a large number of problem. For the functional requirement a system formulation has been developed in order to apply system reliability methods able to provide results faster than with the Monte Carlo simulation.

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